

Single Neuron Chaos

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Abstract

Single neuron dynamics can be mathematically modeled to include chaotic dynamics. Based on the McCullouch-Pitts model, we have shown that the output-input slope is closely related to the standard quadratic map of Feigenbaum. We have adopted a nonlinear mapping of the threshold function consisting of two degrees of dynamic freedom in order to accommodate the refractory and replenishment periods of an axon hillock. By including a third degree of freedom that obeys the quadratic map of Feigenbaum and functions as an internal source term, the final neuron output can produce pulses with a deterministic chaos that depends on the input level.

1. Introduction

In the olfactory bulb, Freeman et al. [1] have demonstrated with EEG a deterministic chaos. The spatially distributed chaos is believed to be useful for dynamic pattern recognition based on a collective response of many neurons. Since in the weak signal limit the smell olden may be seeded by a few sniff of molecules, then it is conjectured that the chaos pattern could be avalanched by a single grand-mother chaos neuron having a time-dependent threshold. This possibility has led us to consider at the single neuron level a simple mechanism that gives rise to chaotic behavior. In this paper, we show that a chaos can be produced by a medium-grained neuron with a dynamic threshold vector $\underline{Q}(t)$ of three components, one of which functions as a Feigenbaum quadratic map derived in this paper from McCullouch and Pitts (M-P) neuron for the first time.

McCullouch and Pitts proposed a constant threshold logic model of a neuron in 1943[2]. Advances in neuroscience since the M-P model was introduced have resulted in a much more detailed understanding of the threshold dynamics of biological neurons[3]. Recent advances in analog VLSI have made possible analog implementation of some neural network models [4] based on the simple threshold logic neurons. These are limited in size to a few hundred M-P neurons due to the communication complexity embedded in two-dimensional planar implementations (about $O(N^2)$ interconnect real estate needed for N simple neurons). This constraint of size-limited neural nets for VLSI implementation has also motivated us to go beyond the simple neurons. A hairy neuron model was proposed by Szu in 1989 [5] to consider two dynamics equations in terms of the singlet firing rate v_i and the pair correlation Hebbian function T_{ij} . This coupled dynamics allows the hairy neuron to prune unused interconnections (by switching off) and grow extra neurites (by switching on) and thereby determine its own interconnection pattern, namely self-architecturing based on a use-it-or-lose-it principle. Here, without yet considering the issue of learning, we study a medium-grained composite neuron model [6] which can explicitly compute the threshold dynamics. The model builds upon the M-P model and thus reduces to the M-P model for weak inputs without exciting the variable threshold dynamics[6].

2. Medium-Grained Neurons with Internal Dynamic Threshold

Following the alphabetic order, we shall always adopt u_i for denoting the net input and v_i the output from an ith neuron. The classical M-P neuron satisfies the sigmoidal function, $\sigma(u_i)$ defined such that the output v_i is related to the net input u_i by

$$v_i = \sigma(u_i) = 1 / (1 + \exp(-u_i / \tau)) \quad (1)$$

where the total input to the ith neuron dendrite is defined as usual:

$$u_i = \sum_j w_{ij} v_j - \theta_i \quad (2)$$

The axon hillock threshold

θ_i is usually assumed for M-P to be time independent. Although the neuron output v_i could be statistically interpreted as the time averaged firing rate of the neuron, say 100 Hz, but in a general case we let v_i model the action potential so that individual pulses and pulse coding can be modeled and produced. In order to produce action potentials within the framework of M-P, we are led to replace the constant threshold θ_i with a changing vector $\underline{\theta}_i(t)$. For a $\underline{\theta}_i$ with two components [6], we can accommodate the refractory and the replenishment periods mathematically with two degrees of freedom related to the potassium and sodium channels in the axon [7].

We can obtain two equivalent dynamic versions of the M-P neuron defined by Eqs(1,2). Transposing the left hand side of Eq(2) to the righthand side, $u_i - [\sum w_{ij} v_j - \theta_i] = 0$ as the fixed zero point, and then multiplying both hand sides with an arbitrary time constant α {righthand side} = $\alpha 0 = 0$, we can assume a local gradient descent that the change of u_i vanishes at the zero point,

$$du_i/dt = -\alpha \{u_i - [\sum w_{ij} v_j - \theta_i]\} = -\alpha \{u_i - \partial H/\partial v_i\} \quad (3)$$

This input dynamics is popularized by Hopfield [8], in terms of a quadratic energy-H landscape concept, namely a Newtonian dynamics-- the force, $-\partial H/\partial v_i$, drives the acceleration of firing rate, du_i/dt . Likewise, the static Eq(1) is transformed into the output dynamics,

$$dv_i/dt = -\alpha \{v_i - \sigma(\sum w_{ij} v_j - \theta_i)\}, \quad (4)$$

as studied extensively by Cohen and Grossberg[9] and recently by Pineda[10]. The two approaches become identical as pointed out by Grossberg [11], when interconnect w_{ij} and threshold θ_i are time-independent for a top-down design of a fixed neural net architecture.

However, when a time-dependent threshold vector $\underline{\theta}_i(t)$ is needed in this paper, we have found that the output dynamics, Eq(4), is more convenient than the input dynamics, Eq(3).

$$dv_i/dt = -\alpha \{v_i - \sigma(\sum_j w_{ij} v_j - |\underline{\theta}_i(t)|)\} \quad (4b).$$

where the L1 norm $|\underline{\theta}_i(t)|$ could be a weighted sum: $|\underline{\theta}_i(t)| = \sum_k c_k \theta_{ik}(t)$.

Moreover, the slope of the sigmoidal transfer function satisfies

$$(dv_i/du_i) = [v_i - v_i^2] / \tau, \quad (5)$$

a Ricatti-like equation, which says the slope vanishes at the unit output (meaning yes) and the zero output (meaning no). Furthermore, in the hard limiting limit $\tau = 0$, the sigmoidal function $\sigma()$ becomes the Heaviside step function $h()$ used in Sect. 4 for its simple point nonlinearity:

$h(x) = 1$ for $x > 0$ and is zero otherwise;

3. Derivations of Feigenbaum Quadratic Flow & Map

The potential at the output may be approximated in discrete time Taylor series as

$$v_i(t_n) = v_i(t_{n-1}) + [dv_i(t_{n-1})/du_i(t_{n-1})] [du_i(t_{n-1})/dt] (t_n - t_{n-1}) + \dots \quad (6)$$

Substituting Eq(5) into Eq(6) yields the finite difference equation

$$v_i(t_n) = v_i(t_{n-1}) + 4\lambda_i v_i(t_{n-1}) [1 - v_i(t_{n-1})]. \quad (7a)$$

where the celebrated lambda knob of Feigenbaum is derived as

$$4\lambda_i = [du_i(t_{n-1})/dt] (t_n - t_{n-1}) / \tau \quad (7b)$$

This finite difference equation can approximate a differential flow, because the assumption of the existence of first order time derivative is implied in the Taylor series expansion. Thus, In the limit of an infinitesimal time, we have derived the Feigenbaum quadratic flow

$$dv_i(t)/dt = 4\lambda_i v_i(t) [1 - v_i(t)].$$

However, to derive the Feigenbaum quadratic mapping:

$$v_i(t_n) = 4\lambda_i v_i(t_{n-1}) [1 - v_i(t_{n-1})].$$

further assumptions are needed. Consider a M-P single neuron that possesses only a single connection from its output to its input. If the threshold is time-dependent and follows the output with a delay of one time step,

$$\theta_i(t_n) = v_i(t_{n-1}), \quad (8)$$

then, with the assumption of single connection feedback weight $w_{ij}=1$, we have

$$u_i(t_n) = \sum w_{ij} v_j(t_n) - \theta_i(t_n) = v_i(t_n) - v_i(t_{n-1}), \quad (9)$$

which lets us write Eq(6) as

$$u_i(t_n) = 4\lambda_i v_i(t_{n-1}) [1 - v_i(t_{n-1})]. \quad (10)$$

Together with Eq(1) which can be rewritten as

$$v_i(t_n) = \sigma(u_i(t_n)), \quad (11)$$

this specifies a discrete dynamics which is the discrete quadratic map of Feigenbaum

$$v_i(t_n) = 4\lambda_i v_i(t_{n-1}) [1 - v_i(t_{n-1})]. \quad (12)$$

which gives rise to chaos. Feigenbaum flow and mapping are clearly not equivalent, but rather is closely related.

We will fix λ_i with a value of one, which, by definition Eq(7b), fix the input change rate per unit time at a constant 4τ . This constant limit is known to Stanislaw Ulam and John von Neumann for a fully developed turbulence on the unit interval. Such a Feigenbaum quadratic map has an exact solution.

4. Threshold Chaos Dynamics

Since we are dealing only with single neuron dynamics in this section, we will suppress the subscript i for the single neuron while keeping index j for those neurons that provide inputs. In order to generalize the M-P neuron model so that a wider range of biological behavior can be modeled, the simplest course of action is to treat the threshold θ as a function of various stimuli including the input firing rate u . This can be justified on biological grounds. A neuron with an axon hillock structure integrates the input signals to the neuron, and if the integrated potential exceeds a critical threshold, generates pulses, followed by a short refractory period during which no pulses are generated. If the threshold is reached, but the input immediately stops, the axon hillock fires anyway. The magnitude of the input signal governs the rate at which pulses are generated. If the input is of insufficient magnitude for the integrated potential to reach the critical threshold, no pulses are generated.

Suppose a time-dependent threshold vector denoted by $\underline{\theta} = \underline{\theta}(\sum w_j v_j, t)$, with vector components that satisfy the nonlinear mapping which is a generalization of Rogers and Szu [10]

$$\theta_1(t) = \theta_1(t-1) - \alpha_1 \theta_1(t-1) + \alpha_1 \sigma(u(t-1)) + \beta_1 [h(\theta_1(t-1)-c) - (3/2) h(\theta_2(t-1) - c)] + \epsilon [\theta_3(t-1) - 1/2] \quad (13)$$

$$\theta_2(t) = \theta_2(t-1) - \alpha_2 [\theta_2(t-1) - \theta_1(t-1)] \quad (14)$$

$$\theta_3(t) = 4 \theta_3(t-1) [1 - \theta_3(t-1)] \quad (15)$$

The two components, Eq(13) and (14) are used to produce the oscillatory phenomenon, which is necessary for the refractory and replenishment of those ions. A second order linear differential equation is usually needed to produce oscillatory phenomena. Here, we prefer a coupled set of first order (piece-wise linear) differential equations, since multiple degrees of freedom may be easily introduced by converting the usual threshold θ from a scalar to a vector, and allowing each component to follow a dynamical equation. The two source terms in Eq(14) are the net input to the neuron $\sigma(u)$, and the effect of θ_3 which we have modeled as the variation of θ_3 from its mean value $1/2$, with a coupling constant ϵ . Eq(15) is recognized as the quadratic map Eq(12), where λ can be interpreted here as a (variable) parameter that takes into account all the factors affecting the population dynamics of the hypothetical ionic species represented by θ_3 . In our simulations, the chaotic output of the grand-mother neuron given by Eq(4b) is approximated with the simple fixed-point step function nonlinearity:

$$v(t) = h(\theta_1(t) - 1/2)$$

5. Simulations

The system of equations Eqs(13-15) has been solved for a sequence of constant input levels $\sigma(u)$ ranging from 0.0 to 0.8 in increments of 0.1, all for a threshold value $c = .25$. The resulting pulse trains are displayed in Fig.1 for a coupling constant value of $\epsilon = .02$. The vertical axis corresponds to the input level with the pulse trains as a function of time superimposed on each constant input line. Input levels of 0.0 and 0.1 resulted in no pulses generated during the time period depicted. At an input level of 0.2 which is slightly less than the threshold parameter $c = .25$, a few pulses are already appearing due to the chaotic driving term. As the input level increases beyond the threshold value, the average frequency is seen to decrease but a seemingly random but really chaotic component to the spacing is maintained. For each input level, the net input $\sigma(u)$ was assumed to be zero for time $t < 0$, with the input jumping up to its constant value at $t=0$. The scale of the time axis is arbitrary in that any time constant can be chosen for the set of equations used.

Fig.2 displays the pulse trains for a coupling constant value of $\epsilon = .05$. All other parameters are the same as in Fig (1). In this case, pulses are seen to be possible for a zero net input level. Since the net input level displayed is actually the weighted sum of inputs after being passed through the sigmoidal transfer function, a net input level of zero in the simulation corresponds to a large inhibitory signal to the neuron. Thus, in this simulation, the neuron will always fire an occasional pulse, even for strong inhibitory inputs. As the input becomes less inhibitory and finally excitatory, the mean frequency of pulse generation is seen to increase.

In Fig.3 we have a phase plot where the difference in starting times of the second and third most recent pulses is plotted as the vertical variable against the difference in starting times of the most recent and second most recent pulses. That is, we have plotted $y = t(\text{pulse } k-1) - t(\text{pulse } k-2)$ versus $x = t(\text{pulse } k) - t(\text{pulse } k-1)$, with successive points connected by line segments. The plot contains 5000 pulses for an input level $\sigma(u) = 0.5$. As expected, the plot demonstrates a chaotic rather than purely random character. Plots of over 100,000 pulses have produced the same non-repeating character as seen in Fig.3.

6. Remarks

While we have dealt in this paper with a discrete mapping, similar behavior could be expected with continuous dynamics. It is known, as Kolmogorov-Arnold-Moser theorem, that an ordinary differential equations (ODE) needs 3 degrees of freedom (three Lyapunov exponents $\lambda_1 > 0$,

$\lambda_2 = 0, \lambda_3 > 0$; an invertible map, 2 degrees of freedom; noninvertible map, 1 degree of freedom, in order to be able to produce chaos.

Our choice of Eqs(9-11) has not been made with the goal of simulating detailed biological behavior, but rather to demonstrate that to the level of fidelity available within the framework of a generalized M-P model. Not only we can duplicate some of the qualitative phenomenology of biological neurons, but also, with a minor modification to the M-P mapping, chaotic behavior among the internal degrees of freedom of our neuron model can easily result. We have shown that the change of input-output slope relationship of the sigmoidal neuron, Eq(3), is closely related to the quadratic map of Feigenbaum or logistic equation, Eq(12). The logistic equation is of interest when considering internal degrees of freedom that correspond to ionic populations because of its applicability to modeling biological populations and the current interest in chaotic cycling in populations and genetics[12].

The dynamical variables in an actual cell that are most important to this pulse generation phenomena are the sodium and potassium currents[7], or equivalently, the populations of sodium and potassium channels. Mead[4] has described an analog VLSI design that behaves in the same qualitative manner as a biological axon. Two internal degrees of freedom allowed us to model an axon hillock. In a real axon hillock, the sodium and potassium currents are the two most important dynamical variables responsible for the generation of the action potential. Thus it is no surprise that an artificial neuron requires two internal degrees of freedom in order to generate an action potential.

We are in agreement with Freeman [1] that the most important advancement of chaotic neurons must come from new information processing paradigm that remains to be challenging and to be elucidated.

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Fig. 1 The output pulse trains of the chaotic neuron model for different constant input values have been superimposed on the constant input values and plotted as a function of time for a coupling constant value $\epsilon = .02$.

Fig. 2 The output pulse trains of the chaotic neuron model for different constant input values have been superimposed on the constant input values and plotted as a function of time for a coupling constant value $\epsilon = .05$.

Fig. 3 Phase plot for pulse spacing. The time delay for pulses $k-1$ and $k-2$ is plotted against the time delay for pulses k and $k-1$ for 1000 pulses. Successive points are connected by line segments.

